

NON-LINGUISTIC MEANS OF REALIZING THE PRAGMATIC FUNCTION OF ADVERTISING TEXT

Yunusova Sh.M.

Associate Professor of TMEI, (PhD)
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Abstract: The article examines the functions and classification of non-linguistic means in advertising discourse. Special attention is paid to pragmatic factors that play a key role in advertising texts aimed at influencing the target audience and attracting consumers' attention. The author analyzes non-verbal components of advertising within the framework of the Uzbek substantive-pragmatic linguistic approach.

Keywords: advertising, advertising text, pragmatics, substantive-pragmatic linguistics, semiotics, non-linguistic means, speech influence.

Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются функции и классификация неязыковых средств в рекламном дискурсе. Особое внимание уделяется прагматическим факторам, играющим ключевую роль в рекламных текстах, основной целью которых выступает воздействие на целевую аудиторию и привлечение внимания потребителей. Автор анализирует невербальные компоненты рекламы в контексте узбекского субстанциально-прагматического направления лингвистики.

Ключевые слова: реклама, рекламный текст, прагматика, субстанциально-прагматическая лингвистика, семиотика, неязыковые средства, речевое воздействие.

In the modern market economy, advertising plays an enormous role. Advertising is a process that people encounter every day and everywhere.

According to the philologist L.G. Feshchenko, "an advertising text is a complex semiotic whole in which there is no place for accidental or communicatively insignificant components, since the solution of a pragmatic task in such a text is always primary. This presupposes equal attention to both its verbal and, which is especially important due to the insufficient study of this aspect of advertising communication, non-verbal components" [Feshchenko, 2003; 232].

Pragmatics studies the possibilities of language as a means of communication in various communicative situations. It is concerned with the purposes of communication and whether these purposes are successfully achieved.

The term "pragmatics" (from the Greek meaning "deed" or "action") was introduced into scientific discourse by one of the founders of semiotics, Charles Morris. Following the ideas of Charles Sanders Peirce, Morris divided semiotics into semantics — the study of the relationship between signs and objects of reality; syntactics — the study of relations between signs; and pragmatics — the study of the relationship between signs and their interpreters, that is, those who use sign systems. Pragmatics, therefore, examines the behavior of signs in real communicative processes [Morris, 1983; 37].

According to E.S. Ivanova [Ivanova, 2002; 197], pragmatics investigates the intentions, goals, expectations, shared views, and interests of communicators, as well as various ways of achieving communicative goals and the conditions under which they are realized. Yu.S. Stepanov distinguishes two aspects of pragmatics, one of which determines the selection of

linguistic means from the available repertoire for the most effective impact [Stepanov, 1985]. G.V. Kolshansky interprets pragmatics as a category for evaluating the effectiveness of a text, incorporating both intra- and extralinguistic factors that contribute to achieving the purpose embedded in the speech act [Kolshansky, 1984; Kairambaeva, 2021; 60].

In Uzbek linguistics, the substantively pragmatic approach, as a new empirical direction, examines linguistic possibilities in connection with such extralinguistic phenomena as the speaker, the listener, their interaction in the communication process, and the communicative situation itself. Traditional pragmatology aims to study communication primarily from the perspective of effectiveness, whereas substantive pragmatism proceeds from the treasury of newly discovered possibilities, relying on the findings of Uzbek language studies as its theoretical foundation.

Developing within the framework of content-syntactic analysis [Mahmudov, 1992], pragmatic text analysis [Hakimov, 1993], and communicative situation analysis [Safarov, 2008], the modern Uzbek substantively pragmatic trend [Mengliyev, 2013] differs significantly from existing global approaches. While international scholarship is mainly oriented toward communicative effectiveness, Uzbek substantive pragmatism “has defined the direction of content pragmatics proceeding from the treasury of discovered and described possibilities” [Ibragimov, 2019; 31].

This approach has demonstrated that the practical realization of an individual’s linguistic potential is inseparably connected with a number of extralinguistic factors, including the personal qualities of communicators, speech strategies and tactics, speech etiquette, communicative culture, worldview, and the level of knowledge of the speaker or listener. By revealing hundreds of specific forms of linguistic potential, substantively pragmatic linguistics emerges as a promising field that determines which of these forms is most effective under particular conditions.

Pragmatic factors play an especially significant role in advertising texts, whose primary purpose is to influence consumers and attract their attention. The non-verbal means used in advertising texts can be classified as follows:

1. The use of brand ambassadors (opinion leaders and celebrities). Such non-verbal means are mainly employed in television and internet advertising.
2. Visualization of the advertised product (infographics, photo and video presentations of goods). When this non-verbal technique is applied, the only verbal element may consist of the advertiser’s phone number. Advertising monitors and banners are among the most convenient tools for this type of advertising.
3. Audio marketing and sound design (the use of rhythmic background accompaniment). This non-verbal means is employed in situations where visual effects alone are considered insufficient. The process of selecting suitable music for advertising is analyzed by experts, and its influence on consumer choice is carefully evaluated.
4. Synesthetic audiovisual effects (for example, the sound of a bottle opening or the fizzing of carbonated beverages). Such non-verbal means are particularly important in promoting certain products and services. For instance, in advertisements for carbonated soft drinks, the sound effect of opening the container and the visual effect resembling a crack in the bottle subconsciously stimulate the consumer’s desire to consume the beverage.

5. Coloristics and psychoacoustics (the influence of color schemes and sound frequencies on consumer trust). Advertising is intended to encourage the purchase of a product or the use of a service, and consumer trust plays a crucial role in this process.

6. Visual storytelling (a logical non-verbal sequence of events). In this type of advertising, the sequence of events unfolds logically, allowing consumers to understand the message without words. The logical progression conveys the advertising objectives of the product manufacturer or service provider.

7. Product placement and native (hidden) non-verbal advertising. Although verbal means may also appear in this type of advertising, they are rarely used directly to promote the product or service itself.

8. Graphic accentuation and variation in font size (changes in the size of letters and symbols). This method is mainly employed in advertisements displayed on advertising monitors and banners. By enlarging or reducing words, letters, punctuation marks, or even entire sentences in comparison with others, advertisers convey implicit communicative intentions.

9. Extralinguistic context (mise-en-scène, stage design, and characters' costumes). The significance of the words used in advertising texts is closely connected with the clothing, scenery, and setting presented in the advertisement.

Non-verbal means are important in advertising because they provide consumers with additional information about a product. Consequently, some advertisements do not use verbal means at all, as non-verbal elements alone are capable of expressing the advantages of goods and services.

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